

Discover Sustainability - Environmental Sustainability Needs Humanities

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Summary: Value systems, goals, beliefs, and worldviews need to be changed to leverage the sustainability transformation within the human society, as they define how humans interact with nature, generate knowledge and technologies, and utilize natural and artificial resources. Therefore, the humanistic values of this era demand the inclusion of environmental sustainability, and building an eco-surplus culture is essential for the social transition away from eco-deficit dystopia. The Topical Collection welcomes viewpoints, reviews, and theoretical and empirical work that are related but not limited to these issues:

- Socio-cultural and economic issues that help mitigate and adapt to climate change and prevent biodiversity loss, as well as support the development and implementation of nature-based solutions and artificial technologies for achieving environmental sustainability;
- Factors that help restore the connection between nature and humans, such as science, art, literature, and lived experiences;
- The psychology towards climate change, biodiversity loss, social transition, and technological transformation;
- The roles of creativity and knowledge management in sustainability transformation;
- Sustainable financing mechanism for climate change mitigation and adaptation as well as biodiversity conservation;
- The roles of urban and rural residents in addressing climate change and biodiversity loss;
- Global agreement, national commitments, and local actions for addressing climate change and biodiversity loss.

Keywords: Nature-human nexus; environmental degradation; climate change; biodiversity loss; community science; citizen science; artificial intelligence; technology; innovations; knowledge management; humanities; adaptation and mitigation; conservation; finance

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